

e-ISSN: 2584-0991

Volume 09 Issue 02
May-Aug 2026

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Smart Vehicle Utilization Monitoring System using GPS & OBD Data Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Smart Vehicle Utilization Monitoring System using GPS and OBD Data Analysis is designed to enable real-time tracking and performance analysis of vehicles through automated data acquisition and visualization. The system collects live vehicle parameters such as engine RPM, speed, coolant temperature, fuel consumption, and location using GPS and OBD-II interfaces. The acquired data is processed using a Python-based backend and displayed on a web-based dashboard for continuous monitoring. The system eliminates manual data handling by enabling automatic and real-time data streaming from the vehicle to the monitoring platform. It provides graphical visualization and performance metrics to support operational analysis and maintenance planning. The implementation is cost-effective, scalable, and does not require complex embedded hardware. This system improves vehicle utilization efficiency, enhances monitoring accuracy, and supports data-driven decision-making for infrastructure and fleet management applications.

Keywords: *Vehicle Monitoring, OBD-II Data Analysis, GPS Tracking, Real-Time Data Visualization*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Smart Vehicle Utilization Monitoring System using GPS and OBD Data Analysis is developed and designed to monitor and analyze vehicle performance and movement using vehicle-generated data. With the increasing use of vehicles in transportation and industrial operations, it is important to track parameters such as speed, fuel consumption, distance travelled, and engine condition. Traditional methods rely on manual recording, which is inefficient and prone to errors, creating a need for an automated monitoring system.

Modern vehicles provide real-time data through the On-Board Diagnostics (OBD) system, which includes engine RPM, vehicle speed, fuel consumption, and engine temperature. GPS provides location and distance information. By collecting and analyzing this data, the system can provide meaningful insights about vehicle performance and usage.

This system contains a web-based dashboard that processes OBD and GPS data and presents important information in the form of graphs, tables, and summary indicators. It helps users easily understand vehicle behaviour and performance. The system is useful for fleet management and vehicle monitoring, as it improves efficiency, reduces manual work, and supports real-time monitoring and analysis.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Vehicle monitoring systems have gained significant attention due to their importance in improving transportation efficiency, safety, and operational control. Early vehicle tracking systems mainly relied on GPS technology to determine vehicle location, speed, and movement patterns. These systems helped fleet managers monitor vehicle routes and detect misuse, but they lacked detailed

insights into the internal performance of the vehicle such as fuel consumption, engine condition, and real-time diagnostics.

With the advancement of automotive electronics, the introduction of On-Board Diagnostics (OBD-II) enabled direct access to vehicle sensor data such as engine RPM, vehicle speed, coolant temperature, and fuel usage. Researchers have explored combining OBD data with GPS information to create intelligent vehicle monitoring systems capable of analyzing both vehicle performance and movement. Such systems allow real-time performance monitoring, fault detection, and predictive maintenance, improving vehicle efficiency and reducing operational costs.

Modern telematics systems integrate GPS tracking and OBD diagnostics with cloud computing and analysis platforms. These systems enable real-time monitoring, remote diagnostics, and visualization dashboards for fleet managers and vehicle owners. Connected vehicle technologies use GPS and cellular communication to provide continuous monitoring, trip analysis, and vehicle health information, which enhances fleet management and safety applications.

In India, intelligent vehicle monitoring systems are also supported by standards such as AIS-140, which mandates GPS-based tracking devices for public transport vehicles to improve safety, monitoring, and operational control. These systems use GPS and communication networks to transmit vehicle data for centralized monitoring and analysis.

Recent research focuses on developing smart dashboards and real-time monitoring platforms that visualize vehicle parameters such as speed, fuel consumption, engine performance, and

distance travelled. These systems help in optimizing vehicle utilization, detecting abnormal behaviour, and improving overall operational efficiency. However, many existing systems require expensive hardware or complex infrastructure, creating a need for low-cost and software-based vehicle monitoring solutions.

The proposed Smart Vehicle Utilization Monitoring System addresses these limitations by using OBD data analysis and visualization techniques to monitor vehicle performance and generate meaningful insights. It provides an efficient, scalable, and cost-effective solution for real-time vehicle monitoring and analysis.

C Ganesh, Suganthi C. [1] Smart Vehicle Tracking and Location Monitoring System for Efficient Fleet Management. The Smart Vehicle Tracking and Location Monitoring System is a modern solution designed to improve fleet management through real-time GPS tracking and intelligent route optimization. It addresses challenges such as inefficient routing, lack of visibility, and high operational costs. The system enables tracking of vehicle locations, trip management, and driver behaviour analysis. Key components include device profiles, location data, and route management. Developed using Angular, ASP.NET, and SQL, it ensures security and scalability. The system enhances fuel efficiency, driver safety, and service delivery. It empowers fleet-based businesses with data-driven insights for better decision-making.

Srinath Iyer, Bhavesh Nathwani, Sourabh Roy, Aradhana Manekar [2] Implementing an OBD-II Module for Real-Time Vehicle Monitoring with the Help of Internet of Things. Though the era of self-driving cars is upon us, intelligent driving can never overtake safe and cautious driving. We present a module that wirelessly transmits real time vehicle sensor data

from vehicle's OBD-2 port to the mobile application of the user. The driving behaviour that are monitored are the ones that influence the likelihood of the driver crashing (for example, speed) or the severity of the crash (for example, seat belt use). These are proxies for crash and injury risk and monitoring a driver's propensity to indulge in such behaviour enables the technology to calculate a risk rating for that driver.

Amr Wahid, Esraa Khaled, Rawan Ahmed, Mina Gamal, Mohab Ashraf, Marwan Ayman [3] Real-Time Vehicle Tracking and Diagnostics Using OBD-II and GPS Technology. The evolution of technology and the increasing demand for safety and luxury have led to the development of advanced tracking solutions with wide-ranging applications. This paper presents an in-depth investigation into the design, implementation, and system architecture of an OBD GPS tracking device. Our device offers real-time vehicle tracking while integrating the On-Board-Diagnostics-II (OBD-II) protocol to provide diagnostic and real-time sensor data. Uniquely, our system architecture adheres to the AUTOSAR (AUTomotive Open System ARchitecture) standard, ensuring a highly modular, scalable, and reliable solution suitable for modern automotive applications.

Krupa Chotai, Siddhant Doshi, Viral, Gandhi, Rahul Ghelani [4] Smart Fleet Monitoring System. Organizations use fleet monitoring systems for example vehicle tracking, driver behaviour analysis, and efficient fleet management. Current systems are designed for commercial use and are of high cost. We present a model of a cheap sensible fleet monitoring system that might be used for non-commercial applications. The system is composed of a device and a Web application. The device reads data such as

speed as well as fuel from the internal network of the connected vehicle and the location of the vehicle and sends them to a remote service. The remote service processes and stores the data. The users use a Web application to view the data about their vehicles in real-time.

Siddhanta Kumar Singh, Ajay Kumar Singh, Anand Sharma [5] OBD-II Intelligent Vehicular Diagnostic System using IoT. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a the most recent trend of Internet technology which is turning vehicles into the group of an entire ecosystem of connected IoT services. IoT in the vehicular sector offers a new experience for the drivers as provides enhanced safety and security, and a new range of product offerings. Identifying the potentially risky behaviours of driving is the most important roles in avoiding dangerous traffic situations. IoT based systems are now used for vehicle and fleet tracking, fault and error detection, analyzing driver behaviour and many other operational needs. The IoT protocols allow us monitoring and controlling remotely, over an existing network which results in improving accuracy, efficiency and security of the system.

Hamed Saghaei [6] Design and implementation of a Fleet Management System Using Novel GPS/GLONASS Tracker and Web-Based Software. Knowing where the vehicles are, what the drivers doing and monitoring every event in real time is the key parameters for a well-managed decision-making process. In this paper, a novel approach for control and monitoring of a fleet management system using three elements including GPS/GLONASS- based automatic vehicle locators (called Rad100), GPRS/SMS GSM cellular network and web-based software (called PayaRadyab) is proposed to show exact position of the desired vehicle on different maps and take

detailed reports of the mission, travelled path, fuel consumption rate, speed limits, and other necessary information according to the customers requests.

I. Md Siddique, S. Molla, M. R. Hasan, and A. A. Siddique [7] Deployment of Advanced and Intelligent Logistics Vehicles with Enhanced Tracking and Security Features. This study focuses on the implementation of modern and intelligent logistics vehicles equipped with advanced tracking and security features. In response to the evolving landscape of logistics management, the proposed system integrates cutting-edge technologies to enhance efficiency and ensure the security of the entire logistics process. The core component of this implementation is the incorporation of state-of-the-art tracking mechanisms, enabling real-time monitoring of vehicle locations and movements. Furthermore, the system addresses the paramount concern of security by introducing advanced security measures. Through the utilization of sophisticated tracking technologies and security protocols, the proposed logistics vehicles aim to safeguard both customer and provider data.

Rybityski, Oleksandr, et al. [8] Using OBD-II Technology for Vehicle Diagnostic and using it in the Information System. This article considers the research of OBD-2 technology for interaction with on-board vehicle systems, the creation of a unified system that can work with different makes and models of cars. The history of OBD-2 technology, its development, existing standards and their implementation in modern cars is described. Basic diagnostic functions are described, with which you can get information about the car, as well as perform its settings and send various commands to it. In addition, the hardware part of the scanner, its technical features,

nuances of interaction with it and the purpose of each of its pins are considered. Also reviewed couple models of scanners that can be used to develop this system.

Aciti, Claudio, Mauricio Urraco, and Elías Todorovich [9] OBD-II vehicle data capture and monitoring system prototype. In this work, a prototype of a system for taking vehicle parameters according to OBD-II skill was designed and built. The prototype is able to read different magnitudes with the vehicle on-board computer, and the data obtained through a USB GPS. A 3G modem and a USB Wifi adapter were added to the developed prototype.

Jain, Ayushi, et al. [10] Improved intelligent fleet management system with data analytics and internet of things (IoT) for smart cities. Considering everyone utilizes vehicles for personal, professional, and a large portion of the fleet industries, vehicle networks play a significant part in smart cities. As the vehicle network expands frequently, it is essential to optimize the extensive vehicle network for the seamless development of smart cities. The intricate networks of the vehicle that are now controlled by manual labour must be greatly reduced, and the whole management system must be made intelligent. In this study, we proposed a cloud-based, sophisticated IoT-based digitization of the fleet management system.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology is divided into five main stages: data acquisition, data transmission, data processing, data storage, and data visualization.

- **Data Acquisition:** The first step involves collecting real-time vehicle data using an OBD-II scanner connected to the vehicle's diagnostic

port. The OBD device retrieves important parameters such as vehicle speed, engine RPM, fuel consumption, coolant temperature, and other engine-related metrics. GPS data, including vehicle location, distance, and movement information, is collected using a GPS module or mobile-based GPS logging application. The OBD scanner transmits the data wirelessly using Bluetooth or Wi-Fi to the connected system.

- **Data Transmission:** The collected data is transmitted automatically to the monitoring system. In the current implementation, the OBD data is extracted directly using Python-based OBD communication or automatically updated CSV log files. This removes the need for manual data entry and ensures continuous and real-time data flow. The system reads the incoming data at regular intervals for processing.
- **Data Processing and Feature Extraction:** Once the data is received, it is processed using Python. The raw data is cleaned to remove missing, inconsistent, or invalid values. The data is then structured and converted into a usable format using data processing libraries such as Pandas. Important features such as average speed, maximum speed, average RPM, fuel consumption, coolant temperature, and total data points are calculated. These features help in analyzing vehicle performance and behavior.
- **Data Storage:** After processing, the structured data is stored in CSV files or a database for further analysis and future reference. This allows historical data tracking and enables comparison between different vehicle usage periods. The storage layer ensures efficient data retrieval when required by the backend system.

- Backend Development:** A backend server is developed using the Flask framework in Python. The backend reads the processed data and provides API endpoints such as /api/summary and /api/obd-data. These APIs send the processed vehicle data in JSON format to the frontend dashboard. The backend ensures smooth communication between the data layer and the user interface.
- Data Visualization and Dashboard:** The frontend dashboard is developed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. It displays real-time vehicle information such as speed, RPM, fuel consumption, and temperature. Charts and summary cards are used to present the data in a clear and interactive format. The dashboard fetches data from the backend APIs and updates automatically, allowing real-time vehicle monitoring.
- System Integration and Real-Time Monitoring:** All components are integrated to create a complete monitoring system. The OBD device continuously sends vehicle data, the backend processes and stores it, and the dashboard displays it in real time. This enables efficient vehicle monitoring without human intervention.

Table 1: - System Functional Modules Implemented.

Module	Description
Data Collection Module	Collects vehicle sensor data using OBD-II
Data Processing Module	Cleans and transforms raw data
Analysis Module	Calculates speed, fuel, and engine metrics
Visualization Module	Displays graphs and dashboard
Monitoring Module	Provides real-time vehicle monitoring

Table 2: -System Functional Modules Implemented.

Module	Tool Used	Function
Data Acquisition	OBD Scanner Application	Captures vehicle sensor data
Data Storage	CSV File System	Stores collected vehicle data
Backend Processing	Python with Flask	Processes and serves data
Data Analysis	Pandas Library	Cleans and analyzes data
Visualization	Chart.js	Generates real-time graphs
User Interface	HTML, CSS, JavaScript	Displays dashboard

4. CONTENT

This paper presents the design and implementation of a Smart Vehicle Monitoring System using GPS and OBD data analysis to monitor and analyze vehicle performance parameters. The system collects important vehicle data such as speed, engine RPM, fuel consumption, and coolant temperature using the OBD interface. The collected data is processed and structured using Python to ensure accuracy and usability. A

backend system is developed using Flask to manage data processing and communication. A web-based dashboard is designed to display the vehicle parameters in real-time using charts and summary statistics. This allows users to monitor vehicle behavior, analyze performance, and identify inefficiencies. The system provides a practical solution for vehicle monitoring and can be extended for real-time tracking, predictive maintenance, and smart transportation application

Fig.1: -Architecture Design

Table 3: -Vehicle Data Parameters Monitored

Parameter	PID Name in System	Unit	Purpose
Engine Speed	Engine RPM	rpm	Indicates engine performance
Vehicle Speed	Vehicle speed	km/h	Shows vehicle movement
Fuel Consumption	Calculated instant fuel consumption	L/100km	Measures fuel efficiency
Coolant Temperature	Engine coolant temperature	°C	Monitors engine heat
Intake Air Temperature	Intake air temperature	°C	Helps analyze engine condition
Distance Travelled	Distance travelled	km	Tracks vehicle usage

5. RESEARCH AND REVIEWS

The proposed Smart Vehicle Monitoring System is analyzed using real-time vehicle diagnostic data collected through an OBD-

II interface. The extracted dataset included key vehicle performance parameters such as Engine RPM, Vehicle Speed, Engine Coolant Temperature, Fuel Consumption,

and Distance Travelled. These parameters were studied to understand vehicle behaviour, performance trends, and operational efficiency.

The collected data is processed and organized using a structured backend system developed in Python. The data is then visualized using an interactive dashboard to observe parameter variations over time. Through this analysis, important insights such as average speed, engine load conditions, fuel efficiency trends, and temperature stability were reviewed. This helped in validating the effectiveness of the proposed system for real-time vehicle monitoring.

The system is also evaluated based on its ability to automatically extract, process, and display vehicle data without manual intervention. The dashboard successfully provided graphical and tabular representations, making it easier to monitor vehicle performance. The review confirms that integrating OBD-II data analysis with a monitoring dashboard provides an efficient and reliable solution for vehicle utilization tracking and

performance analysis.

6. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Result

The Smart Vehicle Utilization Monitoring System is successfully implemented and tested using real-time vehicle diagnostic data collected through the OBD-II interface. The system is able to read the dataset, process vehicle parameters, and display them on the web-based dashboard in both graphical and tabular formats. Key parameters such as Engine RPM, Vehicle Speed, Fuel Consumption, and Engine Coolant Temperature were extracted correctly and visualized using charts.

The system calculated important performance metrics including average speed, maximum speed, average engine RPM, and coolant temperature. The dashboard displayed approximately 2126 data points, confirming that the system can handle large datasets efficiently. The graphical visualization helped in clearly observing parameter variations over time. The system performed reliably without data loss or processing errors.

Table 4: -Vehicle Data Analysis Results

Parameter	Value	Unit
Average Speed	49.34	km/h
Maximum Speed	86.79	km/h
Average Engine RPM	1839	rpm
Maximum Engine RPM	2991	rpm
Average Fuel Consumption	0.322	L/100km
Average Coolant Temperature	88.6	°C
Total Data Points	2126	count

Fig.2: -Overall Vehicle Speed Graph

7. DISCUSSION

The obtained results show that the developed system is capable of effectively monitoring and analyzing vehicle performance. The RPM values observed during operation indicate normal engine functioning, while the speed variations reflect actual vehicle movement patterns. The coolant temperature remained within safe limits, confirming proper engine thermal performance.

The fuel consumption analysis provides useful insights into vehicle efficiency, which can help in identifying inefficient driving conditions. The graphical dashboard makes it easier to understand vehicle behaviour compared to raw data. The system successfully converts raw OBD data into meaningful information that can be used for vehicle monitoring, performance evaluation, and maintenance planning.

Overall, the results confirm that the proposed system is reliable, efficient, and suitable for real-time vehicle monitoring applications.

8. CONCLUSION

The Smart Vehicle Monitoring System

using GPS and OBD data analysis is successfully designed and implemented to monitor vehicle performance and operational parameters. The system is able to collect real-time vehicle diagnostic data through the OBD- II interface and process it using a backend data processing module. Important parameters such as engine RPM, vehicle speed, fuel consumption, and engine coolant temperature were extracted and analyzed effectively.

The developed web-based dashboard provided a clear and interactive visualization of vehicle data through graphs and summary metrics, making it easier to understand vehicle behaviour and performance trends. The system demonstrated its ability to handle large datasets efficiently and convert raw vehicle data into meaningful insights. This helps in improving vehicle monitoring, identifying performance issues, and supporting better maintenance planning.

Overall, the system proves that integrating OBD data analysis with a web-based monitoring system is an effective and practical solution for smart vehicle utilization monitoring. The system is scalable, reliable, and can be further enhanced for real-time monitoring and

advanced analysis applications.

FUTURE SCOPE

The system can be improved by implementing a fully automated real-time data transmission system to a centralized cloud server for remote monitoring of multiple vehicles. Advanced machine learning models can be further enhanced for more accurate maintenance prediction and anomaly detection. Integration with fleet management systems and development of a mobile application can make the system more practical and scalable. These improvements will help in achieving a complete smart vehicle monitoring and management solution.

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